

FAUNA AND ECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TUNLAM BUTTERFLIES (LEPIDOPTERA: NOCTUIDAE)

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Abstract: This article describes the fauna and ecological characteristics of night butterflies (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

Key words: Agroecosystem, butterfly, polyphagous, oligophagous, monophagous, mesophilic, eurybiont, hemixerophilous, hygrophilous.

Introduction

The Noctuidae family of the Lepidoptera family has about 12,000 species and is one of the most diverse families of insects [2]. These insects are also of special importance in the fauna of our country, among which there are specific specialized groups that prefer natural landscapes and anthropogenic ecosystems, as well as highly plastic eurybionts and broad polyphages, including serious pests of agricultural crops. There is. The results of the research conducted by scientists of the world on the study of the consequences of climate change on the example of insectivorous insects predict the rapid spread and expansion of the range of phytophagous insects across geographical regions and the increase in the number of generations due to changes in the life cycle [8].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The fauna of night butterflies of the Khorezm oasis agroecosystem has not been comprehensively studied. In the studies conducted on the study of the ecology of the main pests of Khorezm oasis agroecosystems, the bioecological characteristics of the cotton tundra from grain winged insects were studied, and the scientific basis of controlling the quantity density was described. In the study of the entomofauna of vegetable crops, 29 species belonging to 4 families of pests, including 23 species of moths, were found in vegetable crops [1]. Also, in the latest research on Lepidoptera, 161 species and 1 subspecies of 119 genera belonging to 26 families of Lepidoptera were recorded in agroecosystems.

According to the research results, 16 or 32% of moths are mesophiles. Eurybionts (26%) and hemixerophiles (26%) combined 13 species, and their share in the fauna was equally distributed. There are 8 species belonging to the

hygrophilous ecological group, and their share in the fauna is 16% (Table 1). According to the food specialization of night butterflies, 30 species or 60% of the total lepidoptera fauna are polyphagous. Oligophages take the next step in this regard. Their number of species is 15, and their share is 30%. Monophages consist of at least 5 species, and their share in the fauna is equal to 10%.

CONCLUSION.

10 species of night butterflies belong to spring-summer, 9 species to spring-autumn, 2 species to early summer, 3 species to polycyclic, 9 species to summer, 11 species to summer-autumn ecological groups. 16 or 32% of night butterflies are mesophiles, 13 or 26% are eurybionts, 13 or 26% are hemixerophiles, 8 or 16% are hygrophiles. According to the food specialization of night butterflies, 60% of species are polyphagous. Oligophages take the next step in this regard. Their number of species is 15, and their share is 30%. Monophages consist of 5 species, and their share in the fauna is the least - 10%.

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